

Infodemic Questionnaire 2021. Consumption of news and COVID-19 information.

TIDE Research Group
on Interactive and Distributed
Technologies for Education

Presentation

This study collects data related to COVID-19 news and information consumption. The study is coordinated by the Research and Transfer Center Rizoma Redes (Mexico/Spain), in collaboration with researchers from the Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona (Spain). All information provided in this questionnaire will be treated with confidentiality according to the data protection legislation of your country. The information collected will be exclusively used for academic research. Please, do not share any personal data (e.g. name, ID number, contact information). To get to know more about the information you share and its treatment, please read the information sheet at [xxxx link xxxxx](#) . For more information about Infodemia 2021, please contact the responsible researchers at admirizomaredes@gmail.com.

Do you consent to participate in the present study?

You can abandon the study at any moment without any risks

Yes

No

i. TELL US ABOUT YOURSELF:

Where do you live?:*

1 Mexico

2 Spain

3 Other:

How old are you?*

You are:*

1 Male

2 Female

3 Non-binary

4 I prefer not to say

I. WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW YOUR INFORMATION HABITS

A1. How often do you consume news or other current information?*

- 1 Never
- 2 Almost never
- 3 Sometimes
- 4 Almost always
- 5 Always

A2. How much time do you spend in a day consulting this type of information?*

___ Hours ___ Minutes

A3. According to your interest, what sources of information do you consult to stay informed?*

You can check more than one option

A3.1 Paper press

A3.2 Digital press

A3.3 Radio

A3.4 Television

A3.5 Websites (including blogs)

A3.6 Social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube)

A3.7. Interpersonal communication (Conversations with family/friends)

Other

II. TELL US ABOUT YOUR DIGITAL CONSUMPTION HABITS

How often do you do the following activities?*

	Never	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Most often	Always
B1. Read the news or other information on social media	1	2	3	4	5
B2. Comment news on social media	1	2	3	4	5
B3. Share news on social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter).	1	2	3	4	5
B4. Share information on instant messaging channels (e.g. WhatsApp, Telegram).	1	2	3	4	5

III. NOW, LET'S TALK ABOUT YOUR INFORMATION HABITS IN THE CURRENT PANDEMIC CONTEXT.

C1. How interested are you in the news or other information related to COVID-19?*

- 1 Not interested at all
- 2 Slightly interested
- 3 Moderately interested
- 4 Interested
- 5 Very interested

C2. How often do you consume COVID-19 information on a typical day?*

- 1 Once a day
- 2 A few times a day
- 3 Often
- 4 Whenever I have the opportunity
- 5 Constantly

C3. In the current pandemic context, which media do you prefer to be informed? *

You can check more than one option

C3.1 Paper press

C3.2 Digital press

C3.3 Radio

C3.4 Television

C3.5 Websites (including blogs)

C3.6 Social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube)

C3.7 Interpersonal communication (Conversation with family/friends)

Other

How often have you shared information related to COVID-19 in the following media?*

	Never	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Almost every day	Every day
C4. Social media	1	2	3	4	5
C5. Messaging services (WhatsApp, Telegram, etc.).	1	2	3	4	5
C6. Videoconferences (zoom, skype, meets)	1	2	3	4	5
C7. Phone	1	2	3	4	5

IV. TELL US A LITTLE MORE ABOUT YOUR INFORMATION CONSUMPTION DURING THE PANDEMIC

Respond according to your level of agreement with the following statements:*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
D1. My information consumption has increased during the COVID-19 outbreak	1	2	3	4	5
D2. I find myself well-informed	1	2	3	4	5
D3. There is an excess of information concerning the COVID-19 outbreak	1	2	3	4	5
D4. The news are trustworthy	1	2	3	4	5
D5. The media manipulate us	1	2	3	4	5
D6. The excess of information prevents me from understanding what is happening	1	2	3	4	5

V. LET'S TALK ABOUT TRUSTWORTHY INFORMATION

How much confidence do you have in the information provided by the following sources?*

	Not at all	A little	Some	Acceptable	Very much
E1. Government	1	2	3	4	5
E2. Mass media (press, radio, television, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5
E3. Social media	1	2	3	4	5
E4. Information disseminated by family and friends.	1	2	3	4	5

Which media content have you found most useful to stay informed during the pandemic?*

You can check more than one option

E5.1 Newspaper articles

E5.2 Audiovisual clips

E5.3 Alternative media sites

E5.4 Podcast

E5.5 Infographics

E5.6 News (Digital Press)

E5.7 News Special Reports

E5.8 Videos

Others:

VI. LET'S TALK ABOUT WHEN YOU CONSUME NEWS ONLINE

Indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements*.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
F1. I am used to doing in-depth reading	1	2	3	4	5
F2. I am used to doing a quick reading	1	2	3	4	5
F3. I reflect on the veracity of what I read/see/listen to	1	2	3	4	5
F4. I contrast the information I read/see/listen to with third-party sources	1	2	3	4	5
F5. I verify news-features such as the date, media source, or journalist's name	1	2	3	4	5
F6. I do fact-checking before sharing news on social media	1	2	3	4	5
F7. I can identify fake news	1	2	3	4	5

VII. NOW, PLEASE TELL US A LITTLE ABOUT YOUR EMOTIONS

G1. Tell us about how you are feeling today:*

----- [Open Response]

How would you describe your experience after consuming COVID-19-related news, in what way have you experienced...?*

	Not at all	A little	Somewhat	Very much
G2. Fear	1	2	3	4
G3. Sadness	1	2	3	4
G4. Joy	1	2	3	4
G5. Anger	1	2	3	4
G6. Disgust	1	2	3	4
G7. Surprise	1	2	3	4
G8. Anxiety	1	2	3	4
G9. Uncertainty	1	2	3	4

G10. How would you describe your emotional state in the last year?*

----- [Open Response]

Respond according to your degree of agreement or disagreement*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
G11. The pandemic has affected my physical health	1	2	3	4	5
G12. The COVID-19 outbreak has affected my emotional state	1	2	3	4	5
G13. The excess of information has affected my well-being	1	2	3	4	5
G14. Having a lot of information makes me feel safe	1	2	3	4	5
G15. I prefer to avoid information so as not to alter my emotional state	1	2	3	4	5
G16. I have experienced stress after being exposed to COVID-19 news/information	1	2	3	4	5

G17. Have you experienced any physical or mental discomfort as a result of the pandemic?

Tell us a little more about it if so

G18. Have you received any type of health attention/care?

2 I prefer not to say

1 Yes

0 No

VII. FINALLY, TELL US A LITTLE MORE ABOUT YOURSELF:**What is your education level?***

- 1 Basic education (primary, secondary)
 2. Upper secondary education (high school, baccalaureate or technical vocational education)
 - 3 University degree
 - 4 Postgraduate studies (Master's, Doctorate)
 5. No studies
999. I prefer not to say

What social status would you say you belong to?*

- 5 High
 - 4 Upper-middle
 - 3 Middle-middle
 - 2 Lower-middle
 - 1 Low
- 999 Don't know
999 I prefer not to say

Are you currently working?

- 1 Yes
- 0 No

Thanks for your participation!